

How to Become a Registered CNA

Becoming a certified nursing assistant (CNA) isn't hard. In most states, the process can be completed in under a year. If you want to start working as a CNA, here's how you can do it.

Step #1 - Local requirements

The amount of training required in order to become a CNA varies at the state level. Therefore, the first thing you should do is look into your state's CNA requirements, so you can properly plan how to meet them.

Step #2 - Join a training program

Becoming a CNA requires that you get both theoretical and practical experience. A good CNA training program will help you get both, if you can't find one of those near you, there are other options. You can get clinical CNA training from hospitals, and get the necessary theoretical knowledge from online classes.

How many hours of training you'll need will depend on the regulations in your state.

Step #3 - Take the certification exam

The final step before you can become a registered CNA is the certification exam. In theory, the knowledge you got from the training so far should be enough to get you through the exam. Pass this exam, and congratulations, you've become a CNA!

You can learn more about this line of work by visiting [this site](#).